

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1A: P-AKT & AKT Film

Figure 4-Figure supplement 1A Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: Sib-1 C1, Lane 2: Sib-1 C2,
Lane 3: I-ASD-1 C1, Lane 4 I-ASD-1 C2, Lane 5 I-ASD-1 C3

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 4-Figure supplement 1A Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: Sib-1 C1, Lane 2: Sib-1 C2,
Lane 3: I-ASD-1 C1, Lane 4 I-ASD-1 C2, Lane 5 I-ASD-1 C3

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 4- Figure Supplement 1A: GAPDH for P-AKT (TOP), GAPHD for Total AKT (Bottom)

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Lane 1: Sib-1 C1, Lane 2: Sib-1 C2,
Lane 3: I-ASD-1 C1, Lane 4 I-ASD-1 C2, Lane 5 I-ASD-1 C3

Lane 2 and Lane 3 signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 4-Figure supplement 1A Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: Sib-1 C1, Lane 2: Sib-1 C2,
Lane 3: I-ASD-1 C1, Lane 4 I-ASD-1 C2, Lane 5 I-ASD-1 C3

Lane 2 and Lane 3 signify the lanes indicated by the arrows